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MAPPING FLORAL RESOURCES AT DIFFERENT SCALES

Mappatura delle risorse floreali a diverse scale

Pollinators demand for floral resources to fulfill their lifecycle, i.e. pollen and nectar, varies enormously between species. Whereas resources demanded by solitary bees may be counted in number of flowers, the demand by bumblebees and especially domesticated honeybees are measured in kilograms. Likewise, the supply by different habitats varies enormously. From no to very bee flowers in many habitats, to flower-rich natural habitats and extremely high number of flowers in mass-flowering species such as heather (*Calluna vulgaris*) and crops like oil seed rape. Balancing resource demand and supply shows a lack of floral resources for shorter or longer periods.

The large variation in floral resources demand for different approaches for the quantification of resources. Whereas simple counts of number of flowers/flower heads is appropriate when investigating plots e.g. in flower rich grassland, these methods is by far too time consuming to be efficient in larger landscapes as those utilized by bumblebees and honeybees. Here semi-quantitative expert assessments might be suitable. Despite, the methods applied for the assessments we found that floral resources in agricultural landscapes were limited and only smaller fractions of the landscapes, i.e. semi-natural habitats and a few crop fields, contained floral resources. Compared to the demand by colonies of bumblebees and by honeybees, these landscapes had in-sufficient resources for longer periods. Flower-rich grasslands contained resources for a varied fauna of wild pollinators especially during mid-summer. During spring, such low-intensity grasslands have a limited

number of flowers compared more nutrient rich and lush grasslands that often have mass-flowering *Taraxacum* spp.

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